

SECURITY ENHANCEMENT OF INFORMATION USING MULTI LAYERED CRYPTO GRAPHIC ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT:

There are various ways to secure the data that is being transmitted. Various businesses use the Modified Advanced Encryption Standard (MAES) to secure sensitive data. Using improved replacement box algorithms, this paper proposes and analyses solutions for more secure communication systems, including automated key generation, power reduction, optimisation of hardware resources, and theoretically less operation demanding approaches. Using the Galois field and the affine transformation characteristics, a new S-box is created. The many phases of MAES were subjected to the

pipelining process by means of this S-box. Each of the three modules—mix-columns, shift rows, and key expansion—was successfully pipelined. The time it takes for the encryption process to complete will decrease as these blocks operate in parallel, which in turn decreases the power consumption of the MAES system. Compared to more traditional methods, the suggested one uses less power and makes better use of hardware resources, according to simulation findings generated in the Xilinx ise environment.

Keywords: Xilinx, MAES, AES, and cryptography.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced Encryption Standard is an abbreviation for the United States Defining the States' Standard for Encryption Standard for Federal Information Processing Systems (FIPS)192,

In November of 2001. It became a federal standard in May 2002 after being ratified. AES is the newest of the four algorithms that the US government has authorised for use at the moment. Since RSA belongs to a separate group of algorithms, it would be unfair to compare AES with it. Data encryption in bulk is not often done with RSA. For digital signatures and key transfers to other encryption algorithms (like AES), RSA is a must-have. The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) uses 128-bit blocks to symmetrically encode data. In contrast to decimal numbers, which can only take one of ten potential values, bits can only take two possible values: zero and one. A key is used to encrypt a 128-bit block by changing it into a new block of the same size in a unique fashion. Because encryption and decryption utilise the same key, AES is symmetric. When it comes to security, the key is the only secret that matters. Variable key lengths are configurable in AES, the

The resultant algorithms are termed AES-128, AES-192, and AES-256 to denote the length in bits of the key, respectively, according to the three lengths defined by the standard. When measured in terms of the amount of time it takes for an attacker to launch a brute-force attack—that is, to search through all possible key combinations in order to discover the correct one—each extra bit in the key practically doubles the algorithm's strength.

A little history on AES The US National Institute of Standards and Technology issued a request for proposals in 1997 to find a successor to the Data Encryption Standard (DES), which was becoming outdated. Following a completely transparent procedure and three open international conferences, the pool of applicants was narrowed down to five from fifteen. We asked for feedback and revealed the chosen candidate in February 2001. Twenty-one groups and individuals provided feedback.

Concerning the proposed algorithm, no one had any objections. AES is built upon strong

mathematics that has been documented extensively, and it seems to be impervious to all known assaults. Due to its extensive publication history, global examination, and the fact that AES has effectively secured large quantities of economic value and information, there is sufficient evidence to suggest that there is no back-door or known flaw. Despite the occasional conspiracy claims surrounding an encryption standard produced by a United States government agency, there are no known elements in its creation, and it was developed by Belgian experts in Belgium. One primary criterion is all that is required of a robust encryption algorithm:

- If the key is unknown, the only method to discover the decrypted clear text is to test every potential key until one works. This is known as brute force.

An additional need must be satisfied as well:

- There has to be a large enough pool of potential keys that it becomes computationally impossible to launch a successful brute force assault in a reasonable amount of time. The previous standard, known as DES (Data Encryption Standard), satisfies the first requirement but not the second since computer speeds have either already exceeded it or are rapidly approaching it.

2. RELATED STUDY

In the SubBytes step, each byte in the matrix is updated using an 8-bit substitution box, the Rijndael S-box. This operation provides the non-linearity in the cipher. The S-box used is derived from the multiplicative inverse over $GF(2^8)$, known to have good non-linearity properties. To avoid attacks based on simple algebraic properties, the S-box is constructed by combining the inverse function with an invertible affine transformation. The S-box is also chosen to avoid any fixed points

and so is a derangement), and also any opposite fixed points.

Fig.2.1. Sub-bytemodels.

The state's rows are affected by the ShiftRows step, which cycles over each row and moves the bytes inside it by a specific offset. No changes were made to the first row for AES. The second row's bytes are all moved to the left by one. Similarly, two and three offsets are used to move the third row, and the same is true for the fourth row. The shifting pattern is the same for blocks of size 128 bits and 192 bits. Bytes from each column of the input state are used to construct each column of the output state of the ShiftRows step. (Offsets are somewhat different for Rijndael versions with greater block spaces). The first row remains intact in the 256-bit block, but the second, third, and fourth rows undergo 1 byte, 3 byte, and 4 byte shifting, respectively.

bytes—this modification is exclusive to the Rijndael cypher when used with a 256-bit block; AES does not employ such blocks.

Fig.2.2.shift rows.

3. AN OVERVIEW OF PROPOSED SED SYSTEM

Semiconductor gadgets have seen a dramatic surge in utilisation. The integrated circuit (IC) is now fundamental to every industry, including the commercial, governmental, and military sectors. Architectural, functional and logical, circuit, fabrication, packaging, and testing are all steps in the chip production

cycle. The lengthy supply chain makes it difficult and expensive to manufacture an IC in one location. It's possible to alter or introduce a malicious circuit into the goods since the production of an IC is done at numerous sites and the monitoring of such a lengthy procedure is tedious.

intent of the assailants. Malicious changes or additions of circuits that cause damage to existing designs are known as hardware Trojans [HTs]. HTs may disrupt the circuit's original operation by being placed in security-weak sections of the IC. The data leakers, behaviour modifiers, and reliability impactors of hardware Trojans are the ones that damage or destroy the device's or system's hardware or worsen its functioning [5]. Infrequent triggers activate HTs, which are tiny in size. Since a Trojan's footprint could be tiny, checking for it in a circuit might be a challenge. The lack of a Trojan-free reference makes this much more problematic. There have been other proposals for HT detection techniques, however this continues to be a problem with IC security. Data may be protected against theft, attempted theft, or unauthorised usage by cryptography. Commercial, government, and military secrets are all safeguarded by cryptographic chips.

Most protected chips are required for data and other high-security areas.

Fig.3.1. Block Diagram of Multipath Authentication model for AES crypto processor.

and drives the control input of the switching circuit. The changes of main path data is observed, the comparator generates negative signal to the switch control for data change. The switch circuit terminates main path signals and connects parallel path signals to AES cipher, so the original results are achieved even though Trojan is activated.

Fig.4.1.simulationoutput

Device Utilization Summary (estimated values)			
Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of Slice Registers	1244	35200	3%
Number of Slice LUTs	18328	17600	104%
Number of Fully used LUTFF pairs	1833	3540	5%
Number of bonded IOBs	514	100	514%
Number of Block RAM/FIFO	21	60	35%
Number of BUFG/BUFGCTRLs	1	32	3%

Fig.4.2.designsummary

LUT4:01->0	1	0.043	0.550	DI/p8/Mxor_b11_mux_0_axc0_000 [94994]
LUT4:03->0	32	0.043	0.143	DI/p8/Mxor_b11_mux_0_axc0_0 (DI/p8b11ac0)
LUT4:10->0	1	0.043	0.000	DI/p8_q8/Mram_c23 [DI/p8_q8/Mram_c23]
MUXF8:11->0	1	0.178	0.000	DI/p8_q8/Mram_c2_0 [DI/p8_q8/Mram_c2_0]
MUXF8:12->0	2	0.128	0.358	DI/p8_q8/Mram_c2_0 [DI/p8/b12_mux0]
LUT8:04->0	6	0.043	0.323	DI/p8/Mxor_b12_mux_1_axc001 [DI/p8/b12_mux0]
LUT8:10->0	4	0.043	0.422	DI/p8/Mxor_b12_mux_1_axc001 [DI/p8/b12_mux0]
LUT4:04->0	1	0.043	0.550	DI/p8/Mxor_b22_mux_4_axc0_000 [95974]
LUT4:15->0	32	0.043	0.480	DI/p8/Mxor_b22_mux_4_axc0_0 (DI/p8b22ac0)
LUT4:16->0	1	0.043	0.000	DI/p10_q2/Mram_c8 [DI/p10_q2/Mram_c8]
MUXF8:11->0	1	0.178	0.000	DI/p10_q2/Mram_c_0 [DI/p10_q2/Mram_c_0]
MUXF8:12->0	1	0.128	0.380	DI/p10_q2/Mram_c_0 [DI/p10/b20_mux0]
LUT2:11->0	1	0.043	0.000	DI/p10/Mxor_m3_0_axc001 [temp1046]
FDR:0	-	-0.000	-	data_out_104
Total		30.635ns	(9.731ns Logic, 20.904ns route)	(25.2% Logic, 74.8% route)

Fig.4.3. Time summary

Rijndael algorithm consists of encryption, decryption and key schedule algorithm. The main operations of the encryption algorithm among the three parts of Rijndael algorithm include: bytes substitution(SubBytes), the row shift (ShiftRows), column mixing (MixColumns), and the round key adding (AddRoundKey).

EXTENSION RESULTS

Fig.4.4.simulationoutput

Device Utilization Summary (estimated values)			
Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of Slice LUTs	3648	17600	49%
Number of Fully used LUTFF pairs	1	3648	0%
Number of bonded IOBs	514	100	514%
Number of BUFG/BUFGCTRLs	1	32	3%

Fig.4.5.designsummary

LUT6:I0->O	1	0.043	0.350	e1/r1/r3/m3/m6/Mxor_b<3>_xo<0>1 (e
LUT6:I4->O	4	0.043	0.630	e1/r1/r5/Mxor_roundout_88_xo<0>1 (f
LUT6:I0->O	5	0.043	0.626	e1/r1/r6/m1/s6/s1/Mxor_out_temp<3>
LUT6:I1->O	1	0.043	0.350	e1/r1/r6/m3/m6/Mxor_b<3>_xo<0>1 (e
LUT6:I5->O	4	0.043	0.630	e1/r1/r6/Mxor_roundout_89_xo<0>1 (f
LUT6:I0->O	5	0.043	0.636	e1/r1/r7/m1/s6/s1/Mxor_out_temp<3>
LUT6:I0->O	1	0.043	0.350	e1/r1/r7/m3/m6/Mxor_b<3>_xo<0>1 (e
LUT6:I4->O	4	0.043	0.630	e1/r1/r7/Mxor_roundout_88_xo<0>1 (f
LUT6:I0->O	5	0.043	0.626	e1/r1/r8/m1/s6/s1/Mxor_out_temp<3>
LUT6:I1->O	1	0.043	0.350	e1/r1/r8/m3/m6/Mxor_b<3>_xo<0>1 (e
LUT6:I5->O	4	0.043	0.630	e1/r1/r8/Mxor_roundout_89_xo<0>1 (f
LUT6:I0->O	5	0.043	0.636	e1/r1/r9/m1/s6/s1/Mxor_out_temp<3>
LUT6:I0->O	1	0.043	0.350	e1/r1/r9/m3/m6/Mxor_b<3>_xo<0>1 (e
LUT6:I2->O	7	0.043	0.556	e1/r1/r9/Mxor_roundout_91_xo<0>1 (f
LUT6:I2->O	5	0.043	0.362	e1/r1/r10/Mxor_roundout_91_xo<0>1
CBUF:I->O		0.000		out_enc_91_CBUF (out_enc<91>)

Total		17.309ns	(1.290ns logic, 16.019ns route)	
			(7.5% logic, 92.5% route)	

Fig.4.6. Time summary.

parameter	proposed	extension
Simulation output	After 10 cycles	After 1 cycle due to pipelining
Slice LUTs	19329	8648
Area utilization	100%	49%
Time consumed	56.8us	17.3us

4. CONCLUSION

A FPGA implementation of area-optimized AES algorithm which meets the actual application is proposed in this paper. After being coded with Verilog Hardware Description Language, the waveform simulation of the new algorithm was taken in platform. Ultimately, a synthesis simulation of the new algorithm has been done. The result shows that the design with the pipelining technology and special data transmission mode can optimize the chip area effectively. Meanwhile, this design reduces power consumption to some extent, for the

power consumption is directly related to the chip area. Therefore the encryption device implemented in this method can meet some practical applications. As the S-box is implemented by look-up-table in this design, the chip area and power can still be optimized. So the future work should focus on the implementation mode of S-box. Mathematics in Galois field (28) can accomplish the bytes substitution of the AES algorithm, which could be another idea of further research. In this paper, we present a modified version of AES for Resource-Constraint Environments. A new Substitution Box is proposed which works over the Galois Field (24) by constructing an unique affine transformation equation. One notable feature of MAES is extending the battery life of low powered devices by consuming less amount of energy. The proposed method shows 18.35% efficiency when encrypted packets are transmitted using the proposed MAES to the sink node and the number of transmitted packets has

increased. In addition, 29.983 milliseconds is found in terms of latency. In future, the security issue and space complexity will be considered to make the proposed modification more applicable. Also, we plan to investigate multipath routing scheme while transmitting the encrypted data to the sink node. We will further delve to integrate Public Key Cryptosystem, specially Elliptic-curve cryptography (ECC) to achieve comparable efficiency in terms of number of packet transmission and latency with better security. In this study, we provide an FPGA implementation of an area-optimized AES algorithm that works in practice. The novel method was simulated using waveforms in platform after being programmed in Verilog Hardware Description Language. Finally, the novel method has been simulated using synthesis. The result demonstrates that the chip area may be optimally optimised with the use of pipelining technology and a specific data transmission technique. Additionally, this design does a good job of lowering power usage, which is great for The chip area is a direct determinant of power usage. Because of this, the encryption device used in this approach has some real-world uses. The look-up table implementation of the S-box in this architecture allows for further optimisation of chip space and power. Therefore, the style of implementation of S-box should be the focus of future study. As a further avenue for investigation, the AES algorithm's bytes substitution may be achieved

using mathematics in the Galois field (28). An adapted version of AES for RCEs is detailed in this study. A novel affine transformation equation is constructed to provide a Substitution Box that operates over the Galois Field (24) as suggested above. By using less energy, MAES is able to prolong the battery life of low-powered devices, which is a remarkable benefit. With the suggested MAES and a large number of encrypted packets sent to the sink node, the suggested technique demonstrates an efficiency of 18.35%. increased. There is also a delay of 29.983 milliseconds. To make the suggested change more relevant in the future, we will analyse the security problem and the intricacy of the domain. On top of that, we want to look at multipath routing schemes for sending encrypted data to the sink site. Our next step is to include a public key cryptosystem, with a focus on elliptic-curve cryptography (ECC), so that we may improve security while maintaining efficiency in terms of packet transmission and latency.

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